

Depiction of Family in Buchi Emecheta's Gwendolen (*The Family*)

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Abstract:

Gwendolen is Buchi Emecheta's tenth novel published in 1989 in London. It is also published in US as The Family, which depicts a Jamaican family in a negative light though the title seems to be positive. It is an ironical title given to the novel and shows author's wide range of imagination. The story of the novel is simple but talks about a complex theme of incestuous relation developed in Brillianton family. This research paper examines how the family, shown in the novel, fails to fulfill its responsibilities towards a growing girl.

Keywords: *Buchi Emecheta, Rape, Patriarchal Powers, Incestuous Relationship, The Family, Self-empowerment, Emancipation.*

Introduction:

Buchi Emecheta is a Britain-based Nigerian novelist. She is significant women novelist from the second-generation Nigerian literary tradition. She is known for her crucial thematic concern, which depicts Nigerian aboriginality, patriarchal social structure and Igbo women's struggle for survival. She is also appreciated for her portrayal of female protagonists who suffer a lot due to patriarchal oppression but at end of the novels, they choose their own way of self-empowerment through education. Gwendolen is one of such famous female protagonists, who is continuously raped for few years by her family friend Uncle Jonny in Jamaica and later by her father Winston, when she joins her family in London. She becomes pregnant with her father's child. All this happens in an absence of Gwendolen's mother. Gwendolen who irrespective of all odds, at the end of the novel, leaves her family and goes away with her baby to lead her own life.

Discussion:

Incest means sexual relation or intimacy between immediate family members. The Webster Dictionary defines incest as, "sexual intercourse between persons so closely related that law forbids them to marry". Rape and incest by closed ones are the themes of the novel.

Gwendolen, is a five years old girl, living with her mother Sonia and Granny Naomi. Her father, Wintson, works on ship. He lives away from home. The novel starts with her father's visit to home and he brings many gifts for Gwendolen. She shows her gifts to all her friends and feels very happy and proud. After few days, her mother also leaves for London. Gwendolen feel alone and lives with Granny Naomi. She is very upset because her mother is away from her. At the time of her daddy's departure, she was satisfied because at least her Mummy is with her. However, this time has made her extremely disappointed. Sonia also is not happy to leave her behind. She promises Gwendolen while leaving

that she would send her money to come England soon.

Granny has a boyfriend, Uncle Johnny who has promised Sonia to take care of her mother and daughter. He frequently visits them and helps them in the farm whenever he gets free time. He is a trusted neighbor and family friend. After Sonia's departure to England, all close friends and relatives returned their homes but Uncle Johnny revisits their house, "To ask how they were getting on without Mummy" (Emecheta, *The Family* 20). The same night when Gwendolen is imagining where her Mummy would be and what she would be feeling, she hears voice of Uncle Johnny and Granny who are very happy with Sonia's departure.

She heard Uncle Johnny celebrating. From the sounds of their voices, she could tell they were incredibly happy her Mummy had gone to England. (Emecheta, *The Family* 20)

Newly departed from her parents, five years old Gwendolen is sleeping alone and feeling bad to know that her Granny is happy for Sonia's departure. "For to Gwendolen, it seemed, the end of the world had come" (Emecheta, *The Family* 20). For little Gwendolen her world is around her parents which is now far away from her. Therefore, she feels that it is the end of her world. She experiences a feeling that she always going to miss her Mummy and at the same time she feels jealousy and anger towards Granny Naomi and Uncle Johnny, who every night busy in celebrating their freedom and merriment. They both have made their road clear to spend time with each other. However, as Emecheta writes, "...you had to accept things you could hardly change" (Emecheta, *The Family* 21). Gwendolen soon learns to adjust with this situation. Two years pass and she is now used to with their conversations and noises at night. Now it does not mean anything to her.

Uncle Johnny has kept his eye on Gwendolen. One night, in drunken condition, he comes to be physical with Gwendolen. Emecheta describes,

One such night, she dozed off however, but was woken by Uncle Johnny. He was kneeling on the bamboo bed. He was now touching her face and mouth, telling her not to cry, that he was here to take care of her. She struggled to get up, but he shushed her, telling her not to wake Granny who was very tired and now sleeping. Gwendolen could hear the rise and fall of Granny's snores. The hand Uncle Johnny kept on her mouth was firm, but his other hand touched all her body, as if Uncle Johnny had four hands instead of two. His breath smelt of rum, he had been celebrating with Granny Naomi. They must have had a lot of drink. He put his hand under the bedclothes and tickled her with his fingers. He wanted her to laugh and enjoy his playing with her, but instead fear and shock froze all her emotions. (Emecheta, *The Family* 21-22)

In Uncle Johnny's iron grip, frozen emotions and scared of the situation, Gwendolen thinks, Was this man with the iron grip over her mouth the same Uncle Johnny who used to bring her and Shivorn sweets and lemonade drinks at Christmas, who used to bring her ripe mangoes from the tree during mango season? Was this Uncle Johnny who used to rub oil on her grazed knee? Was this Uncle Johnny who used to call her Juney-Juney and wink at her and she would win back? Was this

Uncle Johnny who Mammy had said cried all night when Granddaddy Richard died because they were friends? What was the matter with Uncle Johnny tonight? (Emecheta, *The Family* 22)

Uncle Johnny represents the tendency of men who keeps in mind their bad intentions towards women's sexuality. As soon as he gets favorable situation, he enters in her bed without thinking of the trust and emotions of that young girl. He tried to compensate his help with Gwendolen's sexuality. He wants to develop physical relationship in return of his care and help towards the family. He is planning a deal with her by saying,

'Your Mammy gone na England to join your Daddy. Dem no want you dere, but me look after you, right? Me help your Granny on de farm and buy you tings, right? We one family nuh. This our secret, right? Don't tell nobody, because they'll say you're a bad gal. You'll do anything for your Uncle Johnny, not so, Juney-Juney? And if you wan' anything, anything at all, just tell me. We good friends now, good, good friends. (Emecheta, *The Family* 22)

Gwendolen cannot listen more. Her mental and physical condition is stressful. She struggles to get herself out of his hands and runs very fast towards the backyard. Confused, scared and hurt Gwendolen cries, "Mummy why you no take me with you?" (Emecheta, *The Family* 22).

Next day, Uncle Johnny comes quite early in the farm to help them. He seems to pay more attention to Granny who is pleased to have a friend like him. However, Gwendolen is in last night's trauma. She is in dilemma that the secret should be revealed or not in front of Granny and other villagers. She does not want Granny to be

worried and unhappy. She does not want to spoil their friendship.

True he was not married to Granny Naomi, but theirs was a respectable relationship. Two middle-aged people, God-fearing and church-going. Yes, Uncle Johnny must be right. He had told her that they were not hurting anybody and that it was her way of showing him she loved him. It seemed at that time a sin not to love Uncle Johnny. He so good to them. (Emecheta, *The Family* 25)

After few days, Mummy sends her some money and letter revealing news that she had a baby boy. With that money Gwendolen's education starts. In addition, Uncle Johnny continues to rape her for many years. This is first sexual exploitation done to Gwendolen by Uncle Johnny who is not her relative but only a family friend.

Gwendolen at the age of fourteen goes to England to live with parents. There she is happy and helps her mother in household works and looks after her siblings. Two years later Sonia goes to Granville, to attend Granny's funeral. In these two years, her father observes her developing sexuality and develops an incestuous relationship with Gwendolen, who is now only sixteen years old immature girl.

He remembered vaguely that when he was overcome by desire he had begged her to give him herself, because he was her Daddy, and if she loved him she would not deny him the little favour. He did not expect Gwendolen to believe him. Men say all kinds of nonsense when roused. No woman with her head rightly screwed on believed such rubbish. But Gwendolen did. The girl was stupid. (Emecheta, *The Family* 144)

Gwendolen, as a bewildered child unknown to the morality loses her innocence when her father, actually most trusted guardian rapes her. The one who is supposed to protect her in her mother's absence is exploiting her. It is very strange that he asks her whether she had any sexual relationship before. That innocent girl confesses Uncle Johnny's behaviour with her, saying, "Yes, Daddy, many times in Granville many times. Almost every night for years" (Emecheta, *The Family* 145).

She is growing fast and facing many incidences to grow mature. In her immaturity, Gwendolen thinks not to lie to her daddy because, "After all, he was her Daddy" (Emecheta, *The Family* 145). However, after hearing her true answer that shameless fellow gets angry and calls her a bitch.

'Shut up, shut up, me say. You bitch. Why youno say so before? You for stay in Jamaica. B . . . bitch. You allow men to trouble you and you no tell me or your Mammy. You wicked gal. Devil gal. Wicked.' (Emecheta, *The Family* 145)

This is paradox that Wintson developing incestuous relationship with her daughter and calling her a bitch. It is double standard of patriarchal attitude that men can do anything they want to but when a woman loses her dignity, they use abusive language for her. They never forgive women and expect that after their own mistakes women should forgive them because they are men, the most superior human beings. With Wintson's character, Emecheta again criticizes men-folk. In Wintson's case, he betrays his wife by having sex with his own daughter. When Sonia comes to know that Gwendolen is pregnant by her own father, she becomes curious and feels shameful in front of Gwendolen. At this time, Gwendolen also develops sexual relationship with her white boyfriend Emmanuel. To this novel,

Emecheta gives modern, optimistic and slightly confusing ending where Gwendolen lives happily in a council flat with her baby Iyamide means 'my mother is here'.

At the end of the novel, her father dies by bomb explosion, her boyfriend remains as a boyfriend and her mother recognizes the biological father of the baby who is Gwendolen's father. Gwendolen as a matured protagonist of Buchi Emecheta handles the complex situation and family relationships with a great ease.

Gwendolen being a victim of sexual exploitation does not want to live in her family. She wants to go away from her family. She wishes to have her family with her baby. She says, "I don't want to go back to my Mum, that's what. I don't hate my parents; it's just that I want to go away from them, to be on my own, in my own room." (Emecheta, *The Family* 179).

Conclusion:

Gwendolen's physical exploitation starts at very young age within her family. When she was unaware of her sexuality and needs her parents' attention, she is left confused, traumatic and frustrated. Her mother is absent whenever Gwendolen needs her. This frustration explodes at the end of the novel when she goes beyond established norms of the society. Her family friend Uncle Johnny, who supposed to be her protector and guardian in her parent's absence but he rapes five year old Gwendolen for many years. The theme of rape is common in the African literature but what Emecheta thinks for Gwendolen is beyond the reader's imagination. Her father, in her mother's absence, rapes her and makes her pregnant. She knows that the child does not belong to her boyfriend Emmanuel with whom she is in sexual relationship for a few days.

Her mother feels ashamed of it but Gwendolen faces this situation by deciding to give birth to her child. Being a rape victim, she

also faces mental trauma but she comes out of it and stands for herself and her baby. She gives birth to a baby girl and decides to live independently. Her father dies in bomb explosion when the hospital nurse and Emmanuel ask the name of her baby's father, Gwendolen replies that he is dead. It is an abrupt ending given to the novel by the author, as Gwendolen is determinant to take her own decisions.

Thus, the novel shows pessimistic side of Gwendolen's family. An institution of family is sacred one, which is supposed to be protector of children but this family turns to be a destructor. Along with rape and incest, Buchi Enecheta also handles few significant themes in this novel like betrayal by father, materialistic obsession,

migration and maternal failures. Being a mature female protagonist of Buchi Enecheta, Gwendolen rejects toxicity of her family and decides to be in her own family in which Iyamide and Gwendolen would live happily ever after.

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